

DiverIMPACTS

Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains Towards Sustainability

Deliverable 7.2

Project website

Planned delivery date (as in DoA): M6, November 2017

Actual submission date: *November 30, 2017*

Work package: WP7

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Version: 1.0

This deliverable is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727482.	
Dissemination Level	
PU Public	PU
CI Classified, as referred to Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Research and Innovation action: GA no. 727482

Start date of the project: June 1st, 2017

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1. Introduction

The DiverIMPACTS project website, created by the Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL, is the central collection and information point for all materials generated in the project and contains all relevant information about the project and its outcome. It is continuously developed further.

According to the grant agreement, the following items are planned to be made available:

- › Project information (list of partners; project aims and work packages);
- › Project news, related news, job postings, events;
- › Publications, dissemination and training materials (stored on Zenodo.org and thus accessible on OpenAire);
- › Crop diversification toolbox to be developed by T6.2;
- › Case study accounts (short info, pictures and logos, links, contact, role in the project; annual update);
- › Videos and photos from success stories from within and outside the project;
- › Communication and promotion materials (project flyer, bi-annual newsletters, press releases, other);
- › Information on the two DiverIMPACTS conferences;
- › Partners' existing tools and social media channels for discussions and communication, especially at a national level;
- › A consumer/general public oriented section, where the benefits of crop diversification will be explained in a clear and straightforward language for lay people.

The project website www.diverimpacts.net went online at the kick-off meeting, which took place in Versailles, France from June 7 to 9, 2017, and contained the basic project information.

The following pages show the current status and further development of the website to consider with plans/suggestions for future activities (highlighted in blue).

2. The website, its contents, features and plans

2.1 Website features

2.1.1 Look and feel

The DiverIMPACTS logo is shown on the upper left and the EU flag on the upper right corner of the website. Orange was chosen as the base colour of the website, corresponding to the orange used in the logo. A lighter orange is used for selected items, e.g. the bar on the right-hand side.

Figure 1: The DiverIMPACTS homepage.

2.1.2 Responsive design

A responsive website can respond to the user's behaviour and environment based on screen size, platform and orientation. The website of the DiverIMPACTS project is responsive - i.e. the project website is mobile-friendly and can be viewed easily on smartphones and other devices.

2.1.3 Integration of Google Maps

Google Maps is integrated on the project website to show the locations of the project partners as well as the case studies. This special feature may be also used for further purposes on the website, e.g. for the field experiments.

Figure 2: Interactive map on the DiverIMPACTS website showing the location of the project partners.

Figure 3: Interactive map on the DiverIMPACTS website showing the location of the case studies.

2.1.4 News archive

The project website contains a feature for the automatic archiving of news. News can also be made available/archived by theme. For instance, all news relating to the case studies are made available on the case study section of the website. Furthermore, all events are displayed on the events page.

2.1.5 Integration of the DiverIMPACTS Twitter account

The DiverIMPACTS Twitter account was created in July 2017. The account contains tweets shared by the DiverIMPACTS project, and related tweets from project partners are retweeted. The DiverIMPACTS Twitter feed is fully integrated into the homepage.

2.2 Website contents

2.2.1 Homepage - www.diverimpacts.net

The homepage contains:

- › An introductory section about DiverIMPACTS;
- › An infobox about DiverIMPACTS with the key coordinates and project information;
- › Contact details of the project coordinator;
- › DiverIMPACTS news;
- › DiverIMPACTS tweets.

Project events and outreach partner activities are announced directly on the homepage or via Twitter.

2.2.2 About - www.diverimpacts.net/about.html

The “About” page of the DiverIMPACTS website informs about the project and its aims in general, the project consortium and the funders; it contains links to related projects and gives a short description of all work packages. The work package descriptions briefly explain their aims and methods and provide contact information of the work package leader and co-leader.

2.2.3 Partners - www.diverimpacts.net/partners.html

At the launch of the website on June 9 2017, the list of partners was provided. The subpages of the partners include the links to the partners’ websites, contact information, descriptions of the partners, their role in the project, a listing of the experts involved as well as the partners’ logos.

At the main page “Partners”, there is an interactive map showing the location of the partner institutions. When clicking on a pin, the contact information of the individual partners as well as a link to their subpage will appear (Figure 2).

A link to the general information about the project consortium can also be found on this subpage.

2.2.4 Case studies - www.diverimpacts.net/case-studies.html

On the case study main page, an interactive map shows the case studies’ location within Europe (Figure 3). When clicking on a pin, the contact information of the case study pops up and leads to the description of the case study on its individual subpage. Furthermore, news items related to activities on the case studies are listed.

The case studies pages were created gradually after the kick-off meeting. The project’s case studies are presented by briefly describing their aim and allocation to the five innovation clusters. Furthermore, their emergence, problems and solutions, as well as the contribution to the overall project aim are described. All pages include pictures, if available, and the contact details of the case study leaders.

At the kick-off meeting, the project partners called for a good visibility of the case studies on the website. Therefore, these pages were created, and the case studies are also strongly promoted via the Twitter account. In October and November 2017, a case study was introduced each day.

Still pending is a description of the five innovation clusters.

Figure 4: Example of a case study description.

2.2.5 Publications - www.diverimpacts.net/publications.html

A link on the “Publications” page leads to the DiverIMPACTS community on www.zenodo.org, where all DiverIMPACTS output created during the project is stored. The publications on Zenodo are automatically uploaded to OpenAIRE. Additionally, selected publications will be highlighted on the DiverIMPACTS website. There is an attempt to create an RSS feed in order to show the latest additions to the SoLACE repository on the website.

Figure 5: The DiverIMPACTS Community on ZENODO.

When storing and publishing the scientific publications (after the embargo period) and other output on Zenodo, DiverIMPACTS ensures that bibliographic metadata are included such as the funding body, the name of the action, acronym and grant number (already predefined in Zenodo), the publication date and a persistent identifier. Via Zenodo, the publications are automatically stored on OpenAIRE, the European Union's electronic gateway for peer-reviewed articles and other important publications (www.openaire.eu).

2.2.6 Service - www.diverimpacts.net/service.html

On the "Service" page, news are archived, upcoming events announced and pictures stored. Furthermore, a registration form is available to subscribe to the project newsletter, which will be issued twice a year. This form is also found in the footer of all DiverIMPACTS pages.

The DiverIMPACTS newsletters will also be made available here.

2.2.7 Further sections to be developed

Three further sections will be developed:

- › Toolbox section: For the toolbox developed in work package 6, a special section will be created and all tools will be made accessible.
- › A conference section will be developed for the two DiverIMPACTS conferences: These sections will include the call for papers, the conference registration, information on the venue and other relevant information.
- › A section for lay people.

2.2.8 Contact/Site info - www.diverimpacts.net/contactsite-info.html

The "Contact/Site information" page shows the contact addresses for the project and the project website, the disclaimer and acknowledgement for the European Union and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) as well as the privacy policy.

3. Social Media

3.1 The DiverIMPACTS Twitter account @DiverIMPACTS

The DiverIMPACTS Twitter was set up in July 2017. The account is used for tweeting information about the project and for retweeting relevant tweets of other institutions and partners. The hashtag to be used is #DiverIMPACTS. The Twitter account is fully embedded into the homepage.

Figure 6: The DiverIMPACTS Twitter account.

3.2 YouTube

A YouTube Account for DiverIMPACTS will be set up by LEAF (Linking Environment and Farming), who is in charge of the project videos.

3.3 Further social media accounts

A Facebook account has been set. It is planned to be used for discussions.

If needed, further accounts, like LinkedIn or Google+, will be considered.

4. Actions for further development of the DiverIMPACTS website

In the coming months the actions outlined below will be implemented. Should new needs arise, necessary steps will be taken.

Actions include to

- Add the interactive map (including information) for the filed experiments;
- Keep the DiverIMPACTS website current with news, tweets and by adding or changing pictures from past events;
- Occassionally update the information and ask work packages leaders for relevant results;
- Remind partners annually to check their websites and send upadtes;
- Add information on the co-innovation clusters;
- Embed the latest DiverIMPACTS publications on the “Publications” page and inc rease visibility;
- Regularly update pictures from past events and gallery updated;
- Develop further sections on the homepage.